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Experiences on taking electronic exams at Tampere University of Technology

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ABSTRACT

In this case study, we have gathered teacher and student experiences on electronic examining system EXAM at a technical university. We will introduce the electronic examination system EXAM, the process of completing an exam and data of user experiences. Computer-based exams are often considered hard or even impossible to use in engineering subject exams but in this research it is shown that both engineering teachers and students find electronic exams easy to use and adaptable. In the spring of 2017 EXAM consortium implemented a national student feedback survey on EXAM. Feedback was collected from almost 750 students and 40 teachers of Tampere University of Technology and the data gathered is analysed and shown in this study. The results indicate that teachers as well as students are generally very satisfied with the electronic exam system and often prefer the electronic version over the traditional paper version.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, Curriculum Development

Keywords: Electronic Examination, assessment, electronic assessment

INTRODUCTION

Different forms of electronic exams in assessment have been used in small-scale for several years at Tampere University of Technology. Because of the nature of engineering studies, lecture hall exams done with a pen and a paper have been the mainstream method of executing final exams not only at Tampere University of Technology but also at other universities in Finland. A need to offer cost-effective examination service suitable for hundreds of students at the same time and lack of cost-effective, computer-aided examination environment was the main promoter to create new forms of electronic assessment environment.

In 2013 a group of universities started a common project to investigate and create a suitable concept for electronic examining. The project eventually created a new electronic exam system EXAM. EXAM concept consists of the exam software (EXAM), customized workstations and network environment, camera-controlled exam rooms and the process to supervise the students. Compared with other online exams e.g. home based exams, these exams done in special premises can be controlled and users are easily identified. Because students can freely choose their examination time and date and are not taking the exam at the same time, the capacity issues are not a problem.

Another big promoter of the electronic examination was the need to assess directly things that literally have been studied during the course, for example coding skills. Naturally, it is nearly impossible to test the use of software with a paper and pen. In an electronic exam, it is possible to take an exam using a specific software and demonstrate the knowledge in that.

It is known that the grading should consist of all the things that are happening in the classroom [4]. In case of courses where there are more than 100 participants, this is not possible but with an electronic exam and continuous assessment, this obstacle can be overcome.

1 BACKGROUND

1.1 EXAM Electronic exam concept

The EXAM electronic exam system is a software system and a concept, which has been developed in cooperation with universities, universities of applied sciences and government funded IT centre for science in Finland. At this moment, there are 24 higher education institutes taking part in the EXAM consortium. This means potential usage of over 200000 students nationally. The project started in 2013 and first deployment was made December 2014 at Tampere University of Technology.

EXAM concept consists of the exam software (EXAM), customized workstation and network environment, camera-controlled exam rooms and the process to supervise the students. EXAM consortium has mainly took part in specifying the EXAM system requirements and the examining process. Exam room implementations are done by each university themselves. EXAM software can be used as a cloud service and end-users access it via web browser so the workstation resources vary between universities depending on their needs. The actual exam comes available at specific time booked and at the specific workstation based on the IP address it has.

Real-time and recording sound and camera surveillance is used for the supervision of electronic exams. Depending on the organisation, also access control and random

check-ups are used. Upon request, the students must authenticate their identity with a recognisable photo identification. Access information at Tampere University of Technology can be combined in order to verify the identity of the person taking the exam and to work out any misuse during exams. Potential cases of disturbance or cheating may be monitored in real time and the camera footage may also be viewed as needed. In Table 1, the EXAM system is presented as functions that are available to students, teachers and administrators.

Administrator	Teacher	Student
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • course data interface • administration of exam rooms • user identification • study register interface for attainments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • creating exams (personal, general, maturity exams) • questions (essay, fill-in, multiple choice) and question bank • assessing and grading exams, also automatic grading • giving personal feedback 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • booking an exam time • taking the exam • receiving personal feedback

Table 1. The functions of the EXAM system

1.2 EXAM process shortly

Examination process starts when a teacher creates an exam and e.g. specifies the exam period when students are allowed to take the exam and the length of the exam. The exam period can vary from one day to years depending on exam, assessment type and also on the capacity issues like amount of available computers.

Exam period also means that students are not taking the exam at the same time but can choose suitable time. Therefore, students can show their skills when they are personally well prepared for it. For teachers, it means that they have to create a question bank from where the questions can be randomized for the students. Also grading differs from traditional paper exams, which are all taken at the same time, as the questions vary and students take them during the whole period set for the exam.

When the student's exam booking is current, the student enters a camera-controlled exam room. Students are able to enter the examination rooms with their student cards. The exam comes available when the student logs in to the EXAM system.

After the student has submitted his/her exam, it comes available for the teacher's evaluation. The evaluation includes assessing the answers, grading the exam and giving personal feedback.

An example of the EXAM examination classroom in Tampere University of Technology is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Electronic examination system EXAM class room

1.3 Benefits of the EXAM system

EXAM system has been welcomed very warmly by students as well as by teachers and positive results in the questionnaire were expected from all the interest groups. Students are positive because they can write their answers electronically, they can choose the time of the exam to fit their own calendar and study rhythm and take the exam when they feel prepared. It is shown that students need very little support in the examination process but teachers often require support and encouragement in using electronic examination [1].

Teachers have praised that EXAM system helps them to actually test what is taught at a course. For example, programming students have to show their coding skills during the exam or a mathematics student takes an exam where questions are solved by using Matlab. Rytönen et al. already showed that students are more willing to take an electronic exam and that it takes a shorter time to finish an electronic exam than a paper based one [3].

At Tampere University of Technology EXAM has shown to fit in such courses where teachers want automatically evaluated exams including multiple-choice questions, personal exams and exams where special software may be used. At the moment, the workstations are equipped with touch screens, Matlab, Mathcad, Pycharm development environment, Excel, Word, Paint and calculator so teachers are able to create exam questions utilizing all this software. This enables the use of various kinds of exams. Also continuous assessment is easily carried out by using weekly exams and midterm exams.

Due to the nature of engineering studies, the electronic exam is not always user-friendly way of assessing students' knowledge. In cases where the assessment requires calculations or drawing and electronic aids are not a standard and are not used in the classroom, the EXAM system is not yet at its best. Therefore, it is acknowledged that paper-based exams still have their place. But as users have been

very happy with the system, all teachers at Tampere University of Technology are encouraged to trial electronic examination and efforts are made to increase the number of exams in the EXAM system.

2 DATA COLLECTION

2.1 Data collection and background information

EXAM consortium implemented a student feedback survey on exams taken in electronic exam room. The electronic exam feedback was collected during February and March 2017. At the Tampere University of Technology the questionnaire was sent to all students who had participated in at least one electronic exam during 2014-2017. Almost 750 students and 40 teachers answered the survey. Also the time stamps of exams taken were collected from the system and evaluated to give find out when students are taking exams.

As seen in the Figure 2. majority of the students who responded had taken 3-5 exams in the EXAM system and as seen in Figure 3, most of them prefer the electronic examination. There seemed to be no big difference on the preference of examination type regardless how many exams students have taken.

Figure 2. How many exams the students have taken in the EXAM system

Figure 3. How students prefer to take their exams

Majority of the teachers that responded to the survey had also examined more than two exams in the system as seen in Figure 4. Thus we can expect them to have a solid experience in the system.

Figure 4. How many exams has a teacher examined in the EXAM system

3 FINDINGS

3.1 Students' views on EXAM system

As expected based on the previous research, most of the students were very content with the electronic examination system. They reported that signing up for an exam is easy, the exam was easy to take in the system and the examination class rooms are well functioning, as seen in Figure 5. We can conclude that taking an electronic exam in EXAM system is very easy to students as they evaluated the easiness on scale from very difficult (1) to very easy (4) and all averages were above 3,5.

Figure 5. Easiness of completing an exam in EXAM system on a scale very difficult (1) to very easy (4).

In the first years when the electronic exam was implemented it was seen that students were insecure how to use the system when taking the exam for the first time. Thus, a test exam was created. Students can enroll, take the test exam in exam premises and explore how the EXAM system works so that in their actual exam they can only concentrate on the subject.

3.2 Teachers' views on EXAM system

The teachers were more positive about the EXAM system than was expected. They also thought that both creating and evaluating the exam is fairly easy. Only creating the questions was seen more challenging as seen in Figure 6. As indicated in literature, teachers were in general more doubtful about the system than the students [1].

Figure 6. Easiness to use EXAM system in examination on a scale from very difficult (1) to very easy (4).

3.3 Time stamps of exams

The time stamps show that most of the exams were done in May and December, which was expected because at that time teaching periods end and traditional final exams take place at Tampere University of Technology. It also indicates that when talking about exams as an evaluation method, summative assessment still take place at the end of a course at Tampere University of Technology. Naturally, it takes time to change teaching and assessment to more formative in which EXAM system is of great help.

Figures also show that students prefer studying during the working days and hours as seen in Figure 7 and 8. When deploying the EXAM system and opening new exam premises Tampere University of Technology staff assumed more interest in using exam premises during the weekends and evenings. Against the assumption, Saturday and Sunday don't show very popular. Also the beginning of the week is not very busy time at the examination rooms.

Figure 7. Day of the week to take exam

Most popular times to take an exam are around noon. The examination rooms are open from 8 a.m. until 11 p.m. but as seen in Figure 8, the end times are not too popular.

Figure 8. Time stamps when the exam has started

When analysing the results more in detail, it was seen that most of the exams that begin early in the morning were done on Friday and the late exam times were used mostly during the Sunday. Also the no-show rates were higher during the weekends, especially on Saturdays as seen in Figure 9. In general the no-show rate was very small. Students attended more than 93% of the booked examination times.

Figure 9. No show rates of weekdays

However, it is still clearly seen from the results that students take the exams every day, also on public holidays, which indicated that they like the flexibility and use the opportunity to study and take exams also during the weekends and late in the evening. This enables students to choose their own study pace more personally and to plan their learning better.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the survey fulfilled expectations. It was slightly surprising that Sundays aren't popular exam days, as expected in the beginning. Also the fact, that the teachers sense of difficultness did not change if they had done one or many exams with system, was unexpected.

The study shows clearly that students prefer electronic exam and are happy with the possibility to choose a time suitable to their own calendar and study rhythm. Neither is the electronic exam system a problem to teachers in technical point of view. The main challenge in increasing the number of exams available in the system, comes down to the attitudes of teachers. There are still many teachers that think that their exam cannot be transferred into electronic format or that are not familiar with the different type of assessment. Also the fact that different type of assessment may require different approach to the whole course can be intimidating [2].

In the future, it would be very interesting to research if the pedagogy of the course changed when the assessment was changed into the electronic format. Likewise, it would be interesting to hear the opinions of students if they have seen any difference in the assessment of the course and if there is a need to study differently for an electronic exam than for a traditional paper-based one. Further it would be interesting to investigate if the time when students book exams are linked to their performance in the exam.

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